

SEROLOGICAL EVIDENCE FOR *Brucella* INFECTION IN CHICKENS IN BENUE STATE, NORTH CENTRAL NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria has a large population of livestock with most animals and poultry kept under traditional husbandry that allows multiple species on the same farm. The aim of the study was to provide serological evidence of brucellosis in chickens as they may be a source of infection with brucella. Serum samples from local chickens on free range and exotic broiler birds on deep-litter were collected over a 12 month period from 4 high livestock density areas of the state namely Gboko, Katsina Ala, Makurdi and Otukpo. The samples were tested using the Rose Bengal plate test (RBPT) as a screening test and positive reactors were further tested using the serum agglutination test (SAT) as a confirmation test. Eighty four (10.9%) of the total 773 samples screened were reactors in the RBPT while twenty four (3.1%) were positive to the SAT. Seventy three (11.3%) of the 648 local chickens tested were positive to the RBPT and twenty one (3.2%) were reactors in the SAT. Eleven (8.8%) of the 125 samples from exotic birds were positive in the RBPT while three (2.4%) were SAT reactors. Local chickens had insignificantly ($P > 0.05$) higher agglutinating antibodies than exotic birds. *Brucella* infection is present in both local chickens and exotic broiler birds in the study area; chickens may serve as a source of infection to other livestock and humans. There is need for a large scale epidemiological investigation of the disease in chickens.

KEYWORDS: Seroprevalence, Brucellosis, Chickens, Benue State, Nigeria

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INTRODUCTION

Brucellosis is considered by the Food and Agricultural (FAO), the World Health Organisation (WHO), and the Office International des Epizooties (OIE) as one of the most widespread zoonoses in the world (Schelling *et al.*, 2003). It is a major veterinary public health challenge as animals are almost exclusively the source of infection for humans (Bronsvort *et al.*, 2009). *Brucella abortus* normally infects cattle causing abortion in pregnant cows, but other animals and man are susceptible (Godfroid *et al.*, 2011). In Africa, the disease is of great importance and varying prevalence rates in animals have been reported (Chukwu, 1985; 1987). Many investigations have indicated that brucellosis is endemic in Nigeria (Halle and Ajogi, 1997; Ocholi *et al.*, 2004; Bertu *et al.*, 2012; Mai *et al.*, 2012). *Brucella* organisms have been isolated from various animals in Nigeria (Eze, 1978; Okoh *et al.*, 1978; Bale and Kumi-Diaka, 1981; Bale and Nuru, 1985; Oladosu *et al.*, 1986; Ocholi *et al.*, 2004; 2005) thereby establishing the presence of the disease in Nigeria.

Chickens are kept in most parts of Nigeria due to their nutritional and economic importance and the local chickens provide an important source of animal protein as well as income in the rural socio-economy with little or no capital investment (Gugong *et al.*, 2012). There are isolated reports of serological evidence of avian brucellosis in different parts of Nigeria (Bale and Nuru, 1982; Abdu *et al.*, 1984; Adesiyun and Abdu, 1984; Chukwu and Anene, 1988; Kudi *et al.*, 1997; Junaidu *et al.*, 2006; Gugong *et al.*, 2012).

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Chickens are reported to be susceptible to brucella infection (Felsenfeld *et al.*, 1951; Angus *et al.*, 1971; Abdallah *et al.*, 1984). The organism has been reported to cause a decrease in egg production in infected flocks with the recovery of brucella from the egg shell, egg yolk, droppings and internal organs of infected birds (Abdallah *et al.*, 1984).

The method of transmission of avian brucellosis is not clearly known. Felsenfeld *et al.* (1951) have shown that *Brucella* infection could be transmitted from chicken to chicken through infected chicken faeces. Infected chickens have been reported to shed the organism in their droppings (Abdallah *et al.*, 1984; Mushi *et al.*, 2008). Kumar *et al.* (1984) reported that following experimental infection, serum agglutination antibodies were present for as long as 5 weeks followed by shedding of the organism in faeces for 4 weeks. Furthermore, infections spread to un-inoculated pen mates, and concluded that normal chickens in contact with *Brucella* infected chickens could also contract infection which may be transferred to the rest of the flock and other livestock.

The raising of chickens by the rural semi-rural households is traditionally practised and most flocks are on free range and kept with other animals such as cattle, sheep and goats (Junaidu *et al.*, 2006). The local chickens are easier to manage been generally reared and kept under free range, mixing freely with other animals and humans. This system predisposes chickens to infection with *Brucella* organisms through contact with these animals, aborted or contaminated materials as documented by Angus *et al.* (1971) who reported the natural transmission of brucella from cattle to chickens. Raising of exotic birds particularly broiler chickens on deep-litter as a small scale business has also become common among the people. There was no report on the occurrence of brucellosis in chickens in the area of study.

This study therefore intends to establish the presence of brucellosis in chickens and the risk posed as reservoir of infection of brucella. The results from this study will also form a baseline data for further research work.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling

Six hundred and forty eight (648) adult local chickens and one hundred and twenty five (125) exotic broiler birds purchased for slaughter in Gboko, Katsina Ala, Makurdi, and Otukpo areas of Benue State, Nigeria were sampled. The local chickens were reared under free range management and originated from different localities within these areas. The exotic birds were reared under deep litter system of management. From each bird, blood sample was collected into clean labelled test tube at the point of slaughter. The blood collected from the birds was allowed to clot and contract. Sera was separated and clarified by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes and stored at -20°C until tested.

Test methods

All sera were screened for agglutinins using the RBPT. The RBPT *Brucella abortus* antigen (Product name: *Brucella* Rose Bengal Test Standard Antigen. Product code: RAA 0060) was obtained from the Veterinary Laboratories Agency –Weybridge, New Haw, Addlestone, Surrey UK and used as recommended. The RBPT was carried out as described by Alton *et al.* (1988). Briefly, one drop of antigen (30µl) and one of the test serum (30µl) were placed on a white ceramic tile plate (marked into 4cm squares) and mixed thoroughly using wooden applicator stick. The plate was hand rocked and left standing for 4 minutes at room temperature. Samples that showed agglutination were recorded as positive while those with no agglutination were recorded negative. Control positive and negative sera were always included as quality control.

The SAT was carried out on the serum samples that were positive to the RBPT as a confirmatory test. The *Brucella abortus* Serum Agglutination Test Antigen (Product code: RAA 0054) was obtained from the Veterinary Laboratories Agency (VLA) – Weybridge, Surrey UK and used as directed (dilution 1:10). Serial double dilution as described by Alton *et al.* (1988) was carried out for each RBPT positive serum sample. The serum antigen mixture was thereafter incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. A positive reaction was a serum antigen mixture with a precipitate at the bottom not disrupted by gentle agitation. For a negative reaction, the serum antigen mixture was turbid and there was no precipitation at the bottom. The antibody titres were also converted

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into international units per ml and reactions at dilution of 1:40 (titre of 40) i.e.50 i.u/ml and above were considered positive (Bale and Nuru 1982).

Statistical analysis

The Seroprevalence proportion was calculated as the number of birds testing positive divided by the total number of birds tested. A *P*-value of less than 0.05 was taken as significant for Chi-square test using SPSS.

RESULTS

Antibodies to *Brucella abortus* were demonstrated in the sera of chickens from all the areas of the state sampled. Of the total 773 serum samples collected from both local and exotic chickens in the study, 84 (10.9%) were RBPT positive while 24 (3.1%) were SAT reactors. Of the 648 serum samples collected from adult local chickens reared under free range, 73 (11.3%) had evidence of *Brucella abortus* antibodies using RBPT. However, only 21 (3.2%) of the local chickens tested were serologically positive by the SAT. Of the 125 serum samples collected from adult exotic broiler birds reared under deep litter system, 11 (8.8%) had evidence of *Brucella* antibodies in the RBPT. However, only 3 (2.4%) of the exotic chickens tested were serological reactors to SAT, reacting at titres of 1:40 (50 i.u/ml) and above (Table 1). Overall, the proportion of seropositive chickens was not significantly ($P > 0.05$) higher in local than exotic chickens. Seropositivity between areas sampled was not significantly ($P > 0.05$) different. Results of the two serodiagnosis tests indicated that RBPT detected higher percentage of seropositive chickens than SAT (Table 1).

DISCUSSION

The overall 10.9% seroprevalence in the RBPT and 3.1% by SAT in this study indicates that brucellosis is present in chickens in Benue State, Nigeria not only in local chickens on free range but also in exotic chickens reared on deep-litter. Since chickens are not usually vaccinated against brucellosis, the presence of positive *Brucella* reactors in this study could be attributed to natural infection by *Brucella* organisms. It has been observed that antibodies against *Brucella* do not persist in fowls for a long period but gradually disappear from the blood (Angus *et al.*, 1971). The low number of positive *Brucella* reactors by SAT in this study despite a relatively high prevalence in the RBPT may be due to the presence of receding *Brucella* antibodies or to cross-reacting antibodies from other organisms which commonly infect poultry for example, *Pasteurella* and *Salmonella* (Bale and Nuru, 1982).

Table 1: Results of serological tests for *Brucella* antibodies in chickens in Benue State, Nigeria

Area	Type of bird	Type of management	Number tested	RBPT positive (%)	SAT positive (%)
Gboko	Local	Free-range	315	37 (11.75)	11 (3.49)
Katsina Ala	Local	Free-range	123	15 (12.20)	4 (3.25)
Makurdi	Local	Free-range	108	11 (10.19)	3 (2.78)
Otukpo	Local	Free-range	102	10 (9.80)	3 (2.94)
Subtotal			648	73 (11.27)	21 (3.24) ^a
Gboko	Exotic	Deep-litter	63	6 (9.52)	2 (3.17)
Makurdi	Exotic	Deep-litter	62	5 (8.06)	1 (1.61)
Subtotal			125	11 (8.80)	3 (2.40) ^a
Total			773	84 (10.87)	24 (3.10)

^aValues in the same column with a common superscript letter are insignificantly different ($P > 0.05$)

The 3.2% reactor rate among local chickens on free range is explained by the fact that local chickens usually lead a near wild existence feeding for themselves and likely been exposed to *Brucella* infected materials. It is noted that private home slaughter of animals is common despite availability of slaughter houses. In absence of adequate waste disposal facilities and practises, *Brucella* contaminated materials could easily be ingested by free ranging birds. The presence of brucella reactors in local chickens in this study agrees with the findings of Bale and Nuru (1982), Chukwu and Anene (1988), and Junaidu *et al.* (2006) who reported 2.9%, 3%, and 2.6% reactor rates in local fowls tested by SAT in Zaria, Anambra State, and Sokoto State, Nigeria respectively. Abdu

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et al. (1984) reported a slightly higher prevalence of 4.1% in fowls in contact with nomadic Fulani herds in Zaria. Kudi *et al.* (1997) reported a very high prevalence of 30% in traditionally managed domestic fowls in Bauchi area of Nigeria using micro titre serum agglutination test (MSAT). On the other hand, Gugong *et al.* (2012) reported a very low prevalence of 0.7% in local chickens in Kaduna State, Nigeria using RBPT. Elsewhere, Mushi *et al.* (2008) reported low (0.9%) prevalence among indigenous chickens in Gaborone, Botswana using the same methods.

The finding of 2.4% prevalence among exotic chickens on deep litter in this investigation is probably due to infection resulting from ingestion of contaminated feed and water. This result agrees with Chukwu and Anene (1988) who found 2.6% reactors among exotic chickens sampled in Anambra State, Nigeria. In contrast, Adesiyun and Abdu (1984) did not find any positive brucella reactor in fowls managed under semi-intensive system in Northern Nigeria. The RBPT detected more positive cases than SAT. This is consistent with the findings of Adesiyun and Abdu (1984) who reported rates of 2.3% and 0.9% for RBPT and SAT respectively. However, Chukwu and Anene (1988) did not find *Brucella* reactors with the RBPT in spite of their presence in the SAT. According to Flad (1983), the RBPT is rapid, simple and sensitive but has low specificity. The RBPT is a rapid qualitative test while the SAT is a quantitative test (Alton *et al.*, 1988). The results of this study suggest that the RBPT and the SAT are useful in the diagnosis of avian brucellosis.

The finding of *Brucella* antibodies in chickens in this study is significant because infected chickens could serve as reservoir of infection for other domestic animals and the zoonotic importance of the disease. Infected chickens could serve as reservoir of infection for other domestic animals and humans around them. The presence of an infected flock poses risk to humans as chicken droppings are commonly used as manure and the organisms may be inhaled as aerosol or dust during the packing process. Eggs contaminated with faeces containing brucella organisms pose a risk especially where good hygienic practices are not strictly observed. Infected chickens can be a source of infection for the household members and abattoir workers during slaughter and processing as no protective measures are taken.

The economic and public health significance of the disease in chickens and livestock should not be overlooked, especially by those involved with handling chickens both at the household and abattoir levels. Farmers may be the most important source of transmission within and between farms that practice mixed farming. Other potential routes of infection for abattoir associated brucellosis include: direct contact, via membranes, wounds and skin cuts or abrasions; inhalation of infectious aerosols and ingestion of infected materials (Bale and Nuru, 1982). The highest rate of infection in abattoir workers was found to be inhalation at the processing stages (Kauffman *et al.*, 1980).

Effective control depends on educating farmers on the dangers of this disease which is known to reduce productivity in livestock herds (McDermott and Arimi, 2002). In view of the possible interspecies transmission of *Brucella* organisms, it is recommended that cattle and chickens are reared separately. Abattoir workers and other people who handle poultry meat are at risk and the use of rubber gloves is recommended to prevent infection. Furthermore, public awareness campaigns to poultry owners and handlers should be used to highlight the dangers of contracting *B. abortus* from chickens. A control programme for brucellosis in Nigeria should take into consideration chickens as one of the reservoirs of brucella.

CONCLUSION

The finding of *Brucella abortus* antibodies in this work indicates the presence of *Brucella* infection in chickens in the area, highlighting the need for an epidemiological investigation of the disease in the domestic fowl and its role in transmitting the infection to other animals and humans.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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